
Emotional Engagement and Its Influence on the Survival of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The inability to adapt to environmental changes, change processes and procedures, most small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) have experienced catastrophic collapse. SMEs have allegedly failed to adjust their governance structure, operations, strategy, management systems, and decision-support capacities to withstand shocks and disruptions. The ability of SMEs in Yenagoa to adapt quickly enough to changes has not been demonstrated. This empirical study therefore aims to examine the relationship between emotional engagement and survival of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The theoretical framework for this study is Social Exchange Theory. The study population consisted of 84 managers and supervisors of small and medium scale enterprises in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Census sampling technique was used for this study. The data analysis was done using Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient. The findings of this study demonstrate the role of employee engagement as critical for small and medium scale enterprises to display adaptability, dynamic capability, and competitiveness. The study therefore recommends that small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State should promote emotional engagement by creating a happy work environment that gives employees a sense of belonging and persuade them to believe in and support the company's mission and values. This will increase adaptability amongst small and medium scale enterprises thus, making them take proactive and/or deliberate action and develop new repositioning tactics to face the unpredictable and complex business climate.

Keywords: Emotional engagement, Survival, Adaptability, Dynamic Capability, and Competitiveness.

1.0 Introduction

Business organizations today deal with a wide range of economic issues, including political unpredictability, economic crises, cutting-edge technologies, and fierce rivalry. To maintain a competitive edge over other industry competitors and achieve organizational vitality, businesses must devise and implement strategies that they can implement, or else they risk going out of business. They must maintain their place in the global market while taking on all impending, unforeseen obstacles.

Small and medium scale enterprises are regarded as essential to economic expansion in Nigeria. They significantly increase savings, employment creation, and per capita income. Additionally, they aid in the expansion of local businesses and industry (Ehiedu et al., 2022). The government and other stakeholders give small and medium scale enterprises a high priority due to their substantial contributions to economic growth. Because these small and medium scale enterprises employ a huge number of people and contribute significantly to the progress of industries and the eradication of poverty, the government sets a high value on their success.

Recently, downsizing, critical skills shortages, restructuring, and an increasingly competitive and unpredictable market are just a few of the factors that define the volatile, highly unstable economic climate in which businesses are expected to operate (Mafini et al., 2013). These considerations put a lot of pressure on firms and people to achieve more with less, with a particular focus on making sure the organization survives in the long run. Due to the constantly changing business environment in which they operate, most enterprises in Yenagoa are progressively going extinct. Therefore, it is now crucial for these companies to figure out how to maintain their long-term viability in the market.

According to Naradda Gamage et al. (2020), the survival of SMEs is also threatened by large-scale firms- MNCs (Multi-National Corporations) and TNCs (Trans-National Corporations) because SMEs lack in resources, have less innovative capabilities, and have fewer ability in international strategies compared to large-scale firms. Considering the significant role SMEs play in the development of any state, failure of these SMEs will result to increased unemployment and poverty (Najib et al., 2021). Energy crises, exchange rate volatility, high inflationary rates brought on by structural budget deficits, the government's preference for fiscal over monetary policies, the lack of independence of monetary policies, political unpredictability, insecurity, stringent monetary policies that impact borrowing costs, and the notable and consistent increase in liquidity in developing nations over the previous forty years are some of the major factors affecting the performance and survival of SMEs, according to kamali Zonouzi et al. (2021). They also contended that variations in the rate of inflation have an impact on the SMEs' unstable cash flow, which lowers their capacity to pay debt interest. Since they narrow the gap between loan servicing and cash flow, these macroeconomic indices put SMEs under financial strain.

Ismail and Naqshbandi (2022) examined internal and external factors influencing the survival of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and noted that changes in consumer preferences, economic conditions, or technological advancements have adversely demand of SMEs, poor cash flow management, inadequate capital, or high debt levels has led to financial instability and hinder survival of SMEs, the inability to differentiate products or services, innovate, and adapt to changing competitive landscapes has also negatively impacted the survival of SMEs, difficulty and/or failure to comply with regulations and laws, limited access to raw materials and infrastructure has threaten the survival of SMEs. Furthermore, poor decision-making, lack of strategic planning, or inadequate risk management has undermined the survival of SMEs. Failure of SMEs to embrace

technological advancement, reach new markets, and stay competitive has also led to SMEs going into extinction. Disruptive relationships with suppliers and partners have adversely affected the survival of SMEs. Unfavourable government trade policies, tariffs, high operating costs, and geopolitical instability are factors affecting the survival of SMEs. Limited access to credit or high borrowing costs have hindered survival of SMEs (Adam & Alarifi, 2021; Ismail & Naqshbandi, 2022; Najib et al., 2021).

Appropriate employee behaviour is an indication of stability in an organization. Accordingly, adequately engaged employees are necessary for a sustainable business. Proactive actions have prevented many organizations from collapsing; therefore, forward-thinking leadership must make timely decisions to implement innovative initiatives. Consequently, obtaining a competitive edge in the corporate sector mostly depends on the level of engagement of the employees. As the industries have started their unexpected fight for the physical, digital, and biological worlds, the survival of established enterprises is becoming more difficult (Schwab et al., 2017). Experts, academics, and practitioners find it difficult to identify new business models, concepts, and strategies because of the complexity of the various industrial technologies (Maresova et al., 2018). Only proactive and creative companies could handle this competitive digitization, claim Carvalho et al. (2018). Organizations must continue to find fresh, creative ways to deal with the age of digital transformation. According to Jaja et al. (2019), survival strategies must be integrated into management at both the strategic and operational levels while taking stakeholders' present and future goals into consideration.

Employee productivity is a good way to gauge the effectiveness of a company. If you do not bring a cheerful attitude and demeanour to the office, you cannot expect to perform at your best. Among these ways of thinking is engaged thinking. As stated by Strom et al. (2014), "successful businesses depend on engaged workers." Kennedy and Daim (2010) pointed out that research indicates a direct correlation between an organization's performance and its workforce's degree of engagement. Engaged workers can help a company in many ways, such as improved performance (Buil et al., 2019), decreased turnover (Haivas et al., 2013), and higher corporate citizenship behaviour (Rasheed et al., 2013).

Disengagement has a range of detrimental effects, including decreased revenue and profits, disgruntled clients, a less safe work environment, and the departure of key personnel (Falkoski, 2012). Nonetheless, there are advantages to participating, like higher output and lower anxiety. The importance of employee engagement demands that it be the company's top priority. Understanding the factors that most affect employee engagement can assist companies in increasing worker participation (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). When workers in a hotel are unsatisfied and psychologically estranged from their managers and organizations, the goals of the company cannot be met (Guion, 2010). A readiness to dedicate oneself to the organization usually follows from employee engagement. To put it simply, the degree of engagement that an employee experiences can affect their capacity to complete tasks that have been delegated to them. The significance of employee engagement in augmenting organizational productivity, employee retention, customer happiness, attaining competitive advantage, and making a substantial contribution to organizational performance and effectiveness has been documented (Brad et al., 2011).

According to Robertson and Markwick (2009), employee engagement is consistently demonstrated as something that the worker provides that can benefit the company through voluntarism, advocacy, skill and talent utilization at the highest level, and support of the company's values and objectives. The study further noted that engaged staff members have a sense of loyalty to their company and involve themselves in ways that go beyond their specific roles to benefit the company. Engaged employees are 20% more likely to perform

20% better than non-engaging employees and to become brand ambassadors for the company (Robertson & Markwick, 2009). Robertson and Markwick (2009) argued that engagement can boost a company's productivity, agility, and profit margin. Fully committing oneself to their work, engaged employees have higher self-efficacy and better well-being, which increases staff support for the company. The advantages of employee engagement for a company are endless, so it is critical that businesses create plans and initiatives to guarantee their workers' engagement, as they are the key to their success (Clement & Eketu, 2019).

A situation where workers are passionate about what they do, feel a sense of commitment to their company, and exert discretionary effort at work is known as employee engagement. Additionally, Hutomo and Mujannah (2023) observed that there is a growing understanding that employee engagement is essential to the success of business operations. An organization that fosters a positive work environment and employs responsible, moral, and hardworking individuals will eventually find success. Employee attitude and turnover rates within a company are significantly influenced by employee engagement. Employee engagement, according to Catteeuw et al. (2007), is the degree to which a worker feels appreciated at work, collaborates well, and is trusted. They maintained that engaged workers look for more creative and efficient ways to increase the value of their company and stay on the job longer.

According to Macey and Schneider (2008), employee engagement is crucial because motivated workers provide higher returns on assets, profitability, and shareholder value than disengaged workers. Given that estimates of employee engagement is falling globally and that roughly 30% of workers are only marginally engaged, it is not surprising that concerns have been raised (Gebauer et al., 2008). According to research conducted in 2013 by the Gallup organization, out of the 100 million full-time employees in America, just 30% are actively engaged, 50% are indifferent, and 20% are actively disengaged (Sorenson, 2013). With the promise of major good consequences like skills, talent, and dedication, the business can achieve its goals and objectives. Such assertions position both physical and emotional engagement as a crucial employee metric focused growth of the firm. Numerous elements have been found to influence workers' levels of engagement in prior study. Employee engagement increases as they get to know their co-workers and exchange ideas and experiences (Juan et al., 2018). This suggests that emotional investment at a high level can have disproportionate effects. According to Aybas and Acar (2017), human resource practices that promote work-life balance, skill development, and high performance can all contribute to higher employee engagement.

There is a dearth of empirical data regarding the relationship between employee engagement and survival of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa state. For instance Biriowu and Ofurum (2020) carried out a theoretical review of extant literature on employee engagement, organizational culture and organizational survival. They found out that when employees were given the power to participate in the decision making, they feel valued, trusted, and will go beyond the demands of the job and ensure that organizational goals are accomplished. The study further noted that effective leadership, communication, reward, recognition, and atmosphere of fairness among others are the drivers of engagement. The authors concluded that employee engagement predicts organizational survival, while organizational culture influences both variables. They recommended that managers should keep their employees engaged to reduce cost of recruiting new employees for the same job. In contrast to the earlier theoretical study, this empirical study aims to examine the relationship between employee engagement and survival of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Maintaining competitiveness and sustainability is a challenge for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). Small and medium-sized businesses must also constantly modify their plans to deal with the economic, political, social, and ecological upheavals that threaten to disrupt their operations and ultimately result in failure and the closing of their businesses. Due to their inability to adapt to environmental changes, change their processes and procedures, most small and medium-sized businesses have experienced catastrophic collapse. SMEs have allegedly failed to adjust their governance structure, operations, strategy, management systems, and decision-support capacities to withstand shocks and disruptions (Boylan & Turner, 2017). The ability of SMEs in Yenagoa to adapt quickly enough to changes has not been demonstrated. More evolution and adaptation are required for them to thrive. It is imperative that they establish organizational cultures that are receptive to change and risk, and that they distribute accountability and responsibility more widely (Linnenluecke, 2017). Examining the connection between emotional engagement and the survival of SMEs in Yenagoa, Bayelsa state, is the goal of this study considering the aforementioned information.

Boylan and Turner (2017) opined that SMEs have failed to act proactively and/or thoughtfully thus making it difficult to satisfy stakeholder requests. The resultant effect of this is divestment, reduced patronage, and profitability. The researchers further opined that given the complexity and unpredictability of the business environment, SMEs have failed to devise repositioning strategies that has adversely affected their survival. The survival of SMEs has also been negatively affected due to their ability to recognize changes in the environment through environment scans, modify their procedures, and rethink their business plan (Kodama, 2019). In addition, lack of and/or improper annual planning by SMEs has also adversely affected their adaptive ability and survival strategy (Boylan & Turner, 2017). According to Kodama (2019) faulty process of developing intellectual capital has negatively affected organizational survival. According to Kurtmollaiev (2020), SMEs have failed to constantly adapt their operations to the reality of the modern world and implement strategies that will help them stay competitive. They have also failed to adopt quick and flexible product innovation that can outperform others; hence their survival is affected (Teece, 2018).

Research Questions

The study seeks to provide answers to the following research questions:

- i. What is the relationship between emotional engagement and adaptability of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa state?
- ii. What is the relationship between emotional engagement and dynamic capability of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa state?
- iii. What is the relationship between emotional engagement and competitiveness of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa state?

Research Hypotheses

The following null research hypotheses were formulated and tested:

1. There is no significant relationship between emotional engagement and adaptability of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa state.
2. There is no significant relationship between the emotional engagement and dynamic capability of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa state.

3. There is no significant relationship between emotional engagement and competitiveness of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Bayelsa state.

2.0 Literature Review

Emotional Engagement

Khan et al. (2019) defines emotional labour at work as the process of managing one's emotions during one's job, which serves as the basis for emotional engagement. When working, those who are emotionally committed in their work typically experience joy or pleasant affective states as well as positive feelings about it. Consequently, emotional engagement is defined as the readiness to dedicate oneself to tasks, goals, or organizational actions that is accompanied by positive emotions, such as pride, excitement, or enthusiasm about actively carrying out and accomplishing those tasks, goals, or activities (Aybas & Acar, 2017; Clement & Eketu, 2019).

Khan et al. (2019) suggest that the basis of employees' emotional engagement is their emotional tie with their employer. The secret to creating a happy work environment is to give employees a sense of belonging and to persuade them to believe in and support the company's mission and values. Positive interpersonal relationships, group dynamics, and managerial techniques are some of the strategies Khan listed for making individuals feel secure and reliable. Engaging with people would give them a sense that their job was valuable, that they were safe in their roles, and that their physical and mental aspirations would be encouraged, according to Khan et al. (2019). Furthermore, engagement was described as "the individual's involvement and satisfaction with as well as enthusiasm for work" by Zanabazar et al. (2023). A third way to define emotional engagement is "the degree to which workers dedicate themselves to a project or person within the company, the amount of effort they put in, and the duration of their stay as a result of that dedication." Moreover, he says it's the willingness to invest one's own time and effort to help one's employer succeed.

Emotional engagement, according to Simanjuntak et al. (2023), is the degree to which people find fulfillment in their work and feel appreciated for it. Saks (2006) adopted Kahn's (1990) idea of role-related work engagement, which maintains that a worker is "present" psychologically in a certain role within the company. According to his concept, the work role and the role of an organization member are the two most crucial obligations for most organizational members. Having stated that, he suggested separating organizational engagement from work engagement.

Most theories of employee engagement emphasize the emotional aspect of engagement at work, according to Saks (2006) and Macey and Schneider (2008). In Macey and Schneider's (2008) proposal, for example, positive affectivity is a part of "trait engagement" and positive affectivity is characterized by eagerness. Emotional engagement is a pointer of "psychological presence," according to Özhan and Kocadere (2020), which indicates that employees have feelings about their work and the organization. This can lead to an increase in overall job satisfaction. Stated differently, people are eager and driven to complete tasks and take an active role in their work. "I feel extremely happy when I am fulfilling my responsibilities at work," was an example item created for this concept. When people who are emotionally committed in their work do well, they feel as though they have accomplished something, according to Huang et al. (2022). As opposed to a fleeting and event-specific state like emotion, engagement is a more permanent affective-motivational state that is not focused on any one thing, event, or behaviour (Salanova & Schaufeli, 2008).

Emotionally engaged workers have strong mental fortitude and energy levels, they are prepared to put effort into their work and persevere in the face of difficulty. Dedication is characterized by feelings of significance, inspiration, passion, pride, and challenge. To put it simply, devotion is a very strong psychological affiliation with one's activity. According to Salanova and Schaufeli (2008), absorption is the final degree of engagement and a component of emotional engagement. It is characterized by total focus and immersion in one's job, which causes time to fly by and makes it impossible to take a break from it. Consequently, zeal and dedication are regarded as indicators of emotional engagement. According to Ndoro and Martins (2019); Nguyen and Pham (2020); and Othman et al. (2019), motivated individuals aim their energy, effort, and tenacity toward a goal, motivation is often regarded to be a psychological process. This understanding is congruent with this. As vigor encapsulates the activation and energy, the effort and persistence of the motivated action, and goal-directness in terms of focusing on a specific work goal, it is considered a motivational concept.

Survival

The corporate world is characterized by unpredictability and unforeseen events that jeopardize the survival of firms. Sales and profitability first drop for businesses that do not handle these uncertainties well. An organization's attempts to carry out its activities to satisfy stakeholders may be disrupted or negatively impacted when these unfavourable tendencies continue. This may result in the company losing clients, friends, and reputation. Neglecting to address these unanticipated events effectively could endanger an organization's ability to survive and continue operating (Odekina, 2022).

According to Okoh et al. (2021), departmental support is critical to an organization's sustainability. Put differently, according to Goldman et al. (2021) it must function as an open system. To secure the support required for their corporate survival, small and medium scale enterprises must appropriately relate to their stakeholders. The way that business function is greatly influenced by a variety of factors, including competitors, shareholders, consumers, suppliers, and regulatory bodies. The survival measures that this study will examine are the adaptability, dynamic capacity, and competitiveness of small and medium scale enterprises.

Effective adaptation to surroundings and resource optimization are critical components of an organization's survival in a fast-paced, highly competitive business environment (Akani, 2015; Odekina, 2022). This is the ongoing operation of a business, especially under trying or hazardous circumstances. Success for an organization should be judged by its longevity as opposed to its financial performance. Decisions like raising salaries, paying out dividends, or making investments in the expansion of the company ought to be subordinated to ensuring the firm's existence, as stated by Goldman et al. (2021). According to Daley Jr. (2020), organizational survival and growth are implicit goals that require financial and human resources. Any organization's main goal should be to survive, according to Odekina (2022). Maintaining this goal in mind makes it easier for the business to accomplish and fulfil its other goals. Okoh et al. (2021) assert that unwritten codes of conduct govern all organizations. It is implied by this that the survival of any organization is a prerequisite for achieving any form of objective.

Adaptability

"Adaptability," as it is used in modern management, has biological origins. According to Sabuhari et al. (2020), adaptability in management refers to an organization's capacity to alter its policies and practices in reaction to changes in the external environment. To fulfil stakeholder requests, it means taking proactive and/or deliberate action. Businesses should always be coming up with new repositioning tactics because of how unpredictable and

complex the business climate may be. Globalization and technological innovation have presented organizations with problems that have compelled them to continuously improve their operating strategies (Reeves and Deimler, 2012). Reeves and Deimler (2012) looked at the competitive advantage of the largest US enterprises and discovered that the top three companies in each industry had decreased by 2% from 1960. By 2008, that number had risen to 14%. The data also demonstrated that profitability leaders over the period were not those with the largest market share. In the same industry, the most profitable market share leaders in 1950 accounted for 34% of the total, but by 2007 that number had fallen to 7%. Business executives today struggle to identify their competitors.

Dynamic Capability

Globalization and technological improvements have forced organizations to be innovative due to external forces (Schoemaker et al., 2018). Kurtmollaiev (2020) asserts that businesses need to continuously modify their operations to reflect the realities of the contemporary environment and put competitive strategies into place. Researchers like Teece et al. (1997) were driven by the necessity to survive to offer the dynamic capabilities (DCs) technique for optimal results. Dynamic capability is what happens when a firm's decision-maker(s) change its present capabilities to remain relevant (Laaksonen & Peltoniemi, 2018). It was defined as the continuous process of developing strategies to sustain the growth of enterprises under the notion of dynamic capabilities (DC). It calls for imagination. Businesses that can innovate products rapidly and adaptably will succeed over others since they can swiftly update their knowledge (Teece, 2018b).

Competitiveness

"Competitiveness" does not have a standard definition. It may refer to the ability of a company to produce and sell high-quality goods, or it may mean to optimize return on investment. Competitive and cost-effective pricing offerings enhance competitive position and promote better performance. "A country or company ability to create greater wealth than competitors" was the definition of competitiveness given in the 1994 World Economic Forum in Lausanne (Neary, 2006).

Competitiveness increases efficiency in operations, management, and organizations. It leads to profitable growth in market share. Competitive companies optimize their human and material resources, maximize stakeholder returns, and generate unique, cost-effective products and services at a reduced expense. According to Francis (2023), developing a competitive strategy is crucial for any kind of business or organization. Three categories were created by Matyja (2016) for the competition: Regular competition occurs when actual results meet the expectations of participating stakeholders; less competitive than usual occurs when actual results fall short of expectations. A more attractive one may tempt stakeholders to move; additionally, when actual results exceed expectations, there is an extra degree of rivalry. Those that support the company are still committed to it.

Theoretical Framework

Social Exchange Theory (SET)

Sociologist George Homans created the social exchange theory. He originally mentioned it in 1958 in his essay "Social Behaviour as Exchange" (Lawler & Thye, 2006). In his research on small groups, Homans noted that each participant received praise or criticism from the group as well as from other participants. Homans made a few suggestions that theorize social behaviour as a trade of time, money, effort, approval, status, power, and other material and immaterial goods (Chuang, 2010). Each bears expenses and offers benefits. People will choose acts that are most likely to yield the highest reward since they expect to be rewarded equally with others they help.

Numerous sociologists and other experts have developed social exchange theory in addition to Homans. In contrast to behaviourism, Peter Michael Blau centred his social exchange theory on ideas like preferences, interests, indifference curves, and supply and demand. Different theorists have adopted different notions and assumptions for their specific applications of the social exchange theory due to these variations in the theory's applicability (Cropanzano et al., 2017). According to social exchange theory, exchange processes produce social behaviour. Maximizing gains and minimizing expenses are the goals of this exchange. Theorist George Homans, a sociologist, contended that individuals consider the advantages and disadvantages of social connections. According to Mitchell et al. (2012), individuals will end or leave a relationship when the dangers are greater than the rewards.

Although this may not always be equal, give and take is a common component of most relationships. According to this idea, the decision of whether the individuals involved will maintain the social affiliation is based on how much weight is given to the advantages and disadvantages of each relationship. According to this idea, an individual will balance the benefits of a social engagement (positive outcome) against the costs of that social connection (negative outcome). Material expenses and benefits, such as cash, time, or a service, may be involved. Intangibles like hard work, acceptance from others, love, pride, guilt, respect, opportunity, and power can also be included. Everybody wants to give less in a relationship or encounter than they receive. People are prone to terminate a relationship when it becomes more costly than rewarding, but they tend to stay in them when the benefits are substantial enough. Many variables influence what is and isn't sufficient, such as an individual's expectations and comparisons with other interactions and relationships (Redmond, 2015). The idea that people seek equity in exchange is another facet of social exchange theory. People are upset with the system when they see inequality because they expect to be compensated equally for bearing the same costs (Redmond, 2015; Ward & Berno, 2011).

3.0 Methodology

The primary population of the study consists of 42 SMEs, and a manager and a supervisor from each of the 42 SME's make up the participants for the study bringing the actual population to 84. Census sampling technique was used for this study. Therefore, all eighty-two participants drawn from 42 SMEs served as the study sample. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire, and a non-parametric test Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was used for the bi-variate analysis.

Testing of Hypothesis 1

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between emotional engagement and adaptability.

Table 1: Relationship between emotional engagement and adaptability
Correlation

			EMT_ENG MT	ADAPTABILI TY
Spearman's rho	EMT_ENGMT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.993**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	80	80
	ADAPTABILITY	Correlation Coefficient	.993**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	80	80

Source: Research Data (SPSS Output), 2024

Table 1 indicates that there is a substantial relationship between the variables, emotional engagement and adaptability. The findings ($\rho = 0.993$ and $P = 0.01$) demonstrate that emotional engagement strongly contributes to, and boosts outcomes associated to adaptability. $\rho > 0.01$ indicates a substantial link and, therefore, a rejection of the null hypothesis, according to the criteria for accepting the null hypothetical statement. $\rho < 0.01$ signifies an insignificant relationship and, therefore, a reaffirmation and acceptance of the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis is rejected since $0.993 > 0.01$, which reiterates the substantial relationship between emotional engagement and adaptability of small and medium-sized businesses in Bayelsa state.

Testing of Hypothesis 2

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between emotional engagement and dynamic capability.

Table 2: Relationship between emotional engagement and dynamic capability
Correlation

			EMT_ENG MT	DYNAMIC_C AP
Spearman's rho	EMT_ENGMT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.995**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	80	80
	DYNAMIC_CAP	Correlation Coefficient	.995**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	80	80

Source: Research Data (SPSS Output), 2024

At the 0.01 level of significance, the correlation between emotional engagement and dynamic capability is found to be significant. The correlation between the variables is demonstrated at $P = 0.01$ and $\rho = 0.995$. According to the criteria for accepting a null hypothetical statement, a relationship is implied to be substantial when $\rho > 0.01$, which means that the null hypothesis is rejected; on the other hand, an insignificant link is implied when $\rho < 0.01$, which implies that the null hypothesis is reaffirmed and accepted. The null hypothesis is

rejected since $0.995 > 0.01$, which reiterates the significant relationship between emotional engagement and dynamic capability of small and medium-sized firms' in Bayelsa state.

Testing of Hypothesis 3

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between emotional engagement and competitiveness.

Table 3: Relationship between emotional engagement and competitiveness Correlation

			EMT_ENG MT	COMPETITIV ENESS
Spearman's rho	EMT_ENGMT	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	1.000**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.
		N	80	80
	COMPETITIVEN ESS	Correlation Coefficient	1.000**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.
		N	80	80

Source: Research Data (SPSS Output), 2024

The relationship between emotional engagement and competitiveness is revealed to be significant at a 0.01 level of significance. The relationship between the variables shows that at a $\rho = 1.000$ and $P = 0.01$. Based on the criteria for null hypothetical statement acceptance, when $\rho > 0.01$, it implies a significant relationship and as such a rejection of the null hypothesis, and $\rho < 0.01$ would imply an insignificant relationship and as such a re-affirmation and acceptance of the null hypothesis. Since $1.000 > 0.01$, the null hypothesis is rejected and restated that there is a significant relationship between emotional engagement and competitiveness of small and medium-sized businesses in Bayelsa state.

Discussion

This section provides an explanation of the relationship between the independent variable and the measures of the dependent variable based on the result from the data analysed.

Emotional Engagement and Adaptability

The result on the relationship between emotional engagement and the measures of survival advance a position which highlights on the positive role of emotional engagement in driving outcomes (adaptability, dynamic capability, and competitiveness) of survival. According to Clement and Eketu (2019), emotional engagement is defined as the readiness to dedicate oneself to tasks, goals, or organizational actions that is accompanied by positive emotions, such as pride, excitement, or enthusiasm about actively carrying out and accomplishing those tasks, goals, or activities. That is, the secret to creating a happy work environment is to give employees a sense of belonging and to persuade them to believe in and support the company's mission and values. When this happens in organisations, the organisation can identify environmental changes through environment scans, adapt their processes, and reconsider their business plans to survive in the turbulent business world (Kodama, 2019). The findings of this study support the position of previous scholars. The findings show that if small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa state promote emotional engagement, they will easily

identify, evaluate, and introduce changes that will improve their chances of surviving. They will also easily modify their processes in reaction to both internal and external variables.

Emotional Engagement and Dynamic Capability

The thrust of the present finding adds to the stock of existing knowledge by providing possible answers to the questions of how and why emotional engagement significantly impacts and contributes towards organisational survival. Emotional engagement is crucial since it gives employees a sense that their job is valuable, they are safe in their roles, and that their physical and mental aspirations will be encouraged (Khan et al., 2019). If small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa state can make employees find fulfillment in their work and feel appreciated for it, it will make the businesses continuously modify their operations to reflect the realities of the contemporary environment and put competitive strategies into place.

Emotional Engagement and Competitiveness

Emotional engagement is a pointer of "psychological presence," according to Özhan and Kocadere (2020), it indicates that employees have feelings about their work and the organization. This can lead to an increase in overall job satisfaction. Employees who are emotionally engaged are eager and driven to complete tasks and take an active role in their work. When employees are emotionally committed to their work, they do well and feel as though they have accomplished something (Huang et al., 2022). If small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa state continue to emotionally engage employees, their actual results will meet and exceed the expectations of participating stakeholders thus making them more competitive and attractive.

4.0 Conclusion

The relationship between employee engagement and survival of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State has been revealed to be positive and significant. The findings of this study demonstrate the role of employee engagement as critical for small and medium scale enterprises to display adaptability, dynamic capability, and competitiveness. In line with the results, the study concludes as follows:

Emotional engagement is positively and significantly related to the outcomes of survival (adaptability, dynamic capability, and competitiveness). This means that emotional engagement which emphasizes the degree to which people find fulfillment in their work and feel appreciated for it contributes toward improved survival outcomes such as adaptability, dynamic capability, and competitiveness because the small and medium scale enterprises make employees find fulfillment in their work and feel appreciated for it.

The findings further align with the views of prior studies in its assertion that the degree to which employee is engaged has a substantial bearing on the challenges that businesses confront in the current economic climate. This is because "engaged" employees are dedicated to their work and their organization, thus, bringing about higher organizational performance and success.

5.0 Recommendations

The relationship between employee engagement and survival of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is established herein as significant and positive in the sense that actions or expressions of emotional engagement can be considered as positively impacting and facilitating survival outcomes such as adaptability, dynamic capability, and

competitiveness. Thus, in line with the findings of this study, the following recommendations are put forward:

- i. Small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State should promote emotional engagement by creating a happy work environment that gives employees a sense of belonging and persuade them to believe in and support the company's mission and values. This will increase adaptability amongst small and medium scale enterprises thus, making them take proactive and/or deliberate action and develop new repositioning tactics to face the unpredictable and complex business climate.
- ii. Small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State should promote emotional engagement by taking deliberate steps to increase employee's readiness to dedicate themselves to tasks, goals, or organizational actions. This will enhance dynamic capability of these firms by generating new resources and modifying existing resource base concerned with their current actions.
- iii. Small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State should promote emotional engagement by increasing workers dedication to projects or persons within the company, the amount of effort they put in, and the duration of their stay because of that dedication as this will improve the firm's competitiveness by increasing efficiency in operations, management, profitability and market share.

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